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Exploring the Interdisciplinary Connections: The Role of Medical Humanities in Understanding Illness and Healing

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Abstract:

Medical Humanities is an interdisciplinary field that explores the human aspects of medicine through literature, art, ethics, history, and philosophy. It is indeed emerging interdisciplinary field that bridges literature, medicine, and ethics, focusing on human experiences of illness, suffering, healing, and care. The contemporary Indian English novels have increasingly engaged with medical humanities, addressing health crises, body politics, mental health, pandemics, and medical ethics. The present paper explores how Indian English novelists use literature to decode emotional, social, and cultural dimensions of medicines. It also examines how contemporary Indian English novelists like Arundhati Roy, Manjula Padmanabhan, Anita Nair, and Amitav Ghosh employ literary strategies to humanize medicine, critique healthcare systems, and present illness as a lived social reality.

Keywords: Medical Humanities, Trauma, Mental Health, Pandemics, Body Politics, Medical ethics.

The concept of the Medical Humanities emerged in the 1960s and 1970s in the United States and Europe. It had been developed as a response to an increasing dominance of scientific

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and technical approaches in medicine, which often overlooked emotional and psychological needs of patients. Early pioneers like Dr. Edmund Pellegrino and Howard Brody advocated for integrating humanities into medical education to humanize the practice of medicines. Over the time, Medical Humanities programs began to flourish in medical schools around the world aiming to balance scientific knowledge with ethical sensitivity and human compassion.

Medical humanities is an interdisciplinary field of medicine which includes the humanities, social science (psychology, medical sociology, medical anthropology, cultural studies, health geography) and the arts (literature, theatre, film, and visual arts) and their application to medical education and practice (Aull 2011). Medical humanities can also be regarded as an interdisciplinary and increasingly international endeavors that draw on the creative and intellectual strengths of diverse disciplines, including literature, art, creative writing, drama, film, music, philosophy, anthropology and history, in pursuit of medical educational goals (Kirklin 2003)”.

Medical Humanities provides a critical lens to understand illness not just as a biological phenomenon but also as a lived human experience. It integrates literature, art, ethics, history and social sciences to offer a holistic understanding of health and illness. It bridges the gap between medicine and human experience emphasizing patient narratives and cultural contexts of healthcare. It focuses on understanding patients not merely cases but individuals with unique experiences.

According to Howard Brody, “The Medical Humanities enable healthcare professionals to understand the stories of illness and respond with empathy and compassion” (Brody 4). The Medical Humanities connect various disciplines to foster a deeper understanding of health, illness, suffering and death. It challenges the rigid boundaries of clinical medicine by

emphasizing emotional, psychological and social aspects of healthcare. Sayantani Das Gupta and Marsha Hurst argue that “the stories of illness are essential tools for healing, not only for patients but also for healthcare providers” (Gupta and Hurst 12). The narratives offer valuable insights into patient experiences that medical data alone cannot provide. In his *The Wounded Storyteller* Arthur W. Frank states, “Patients become storytellers, using narratives to reclaim agency from disease” (Frank 55). According to Jones, “Medical Humanities is the application of humanities disciplines to the context of medical education and practice to foster better understanding of illness, suffering, and human experience” (Jones et al. 45). Hence, we observe that the Medical Humanities focuses on exploring illness beyond clinical definitions centering on patient narratives, cultural contexts and ethical considerations.

Das Gupta and Charon explain, “Training in Medical Humanities allows future doctors to listen more carefully, interpret patient stories with insight and respond with compassion” (Gupta and Charon 89). Furthermore it helps addressing issues such as medical ethics, cultural competence, mental health awareness, and the psychological impact of illness on patients and families.

Literature plays a significant role in representing illness and suffering. Illness memoirs, autobiographies, and fictional narratives offer diverse perspectives on the experience of being ill. Visual arts, films and music often represent illness and healing in powerful ways. They help doctors to understand the unspoken emotions of patients. Medical Humanities addresses bioethical issues like patient autonomy, informed consent and medical confidentiality. By studying ethical dilemmas in literature and real-life cases, medical students develop moral sensitivity, essential for professional practice. The Indian English literature, deeply rooted in social realities, naturally, incorporates medical humanities concerns, addressing themes like

mental health, disease, body politics, and medical exploitation. The socio-political landscape of India—marked by poverty, gender inequality, caste discrimination and inadequate healthcare—provides fertile ground for such literary engagements (Das 15). Literature thus becomes a therapeutic space, both for writers and readers (Mukherjee 137). In the context of Indian English novels, themes of disease, mental health, and healthcare inequality reveal layered narratives of suffering, resilience, and socio-political commentary (Das 15). The Indian context offers a rich terrain where caste, class, gender, and health intersect, allowing literature to question the power structures within medical discourses.

In India, Medical Humanities is gaining attention in medical colleges. Novels by Indian authors like Jhumpa Lahiri and Amitav Ghosh explore themes of illness, migration, and social inequality. For instance, Lahiri's *Interpreter of Maladies* addresses communication barriers between patients and doctors, while Ghosh's *The Hungry Tide* highlights environmental health issues. They illustrate how literature can enhance cultural competence in healthcare. Jhumpa Lahiri's short story *Interpreter of Maladies* can be illustrated as a remarkable example of Medical Humanities because it explores the emotional suffering of individuals and the crucial role of communication in the healing process. Mr. Kapasi in the short story works as an interpreter for a doctor, translating patients' health complaints. His character symbolizes the importance of communication in healthcare. Lahiri writes, "He was responsible for helping them communicate, for aiding in the process of healing" (Lahiri 50). It highlights the way interpreters and healthcare professionals contribute to the patient's recovery beyond mere physical treatment. Furthermore Mrs. Das suffers from an emotional illness rather than a physical one. Her guilt over an extramarital affair leads to emotional distress, which she confesses to Mr. Kapasi: "I feel terrible looking at my children sometimes. I feel terrible because I have ruined my own life"

(Lahiri 65). The moment mirrors a doctor-patient interaction, where a patient seeks emotional healing through confession. However Mr. Kapasi's inability to provide comfort reveals the limitations of the caregiver in dealing with emotional suffering. Lahiri also presents the theme of communication breakdown, a critical concern in Medical Humanities. Mr. Kapasi reflects on his isolation, stating, "So very few guests took the trouble to speak to him... They were only mildly curious about his other job" (Lahiri 52). It shows the lack of empathy and understanding in human interactions, often witnessed in medical settings. Thus, Lahiri's story powerfully represents the ideas of Medical Humanities, emphasizing that healing is not limited to medicine but deeply connected to empathy, communication, and emotional care.

The Hungry Tide (2004) by Amitav Ghosh, though primarily an ecological novel, intersects with Medical Humanities through its portrayal of health crises, traditional healing practices, and the struggle of marginalized communities for survival and healthcare access in the Sundarbans. The novel portrays the Sundarbans not only a geographical space but also a site where human vulnerability to disease and nature's unpredictability co-exist. The environment, marked by tides, storms, and wildlife, exposes the local population to physical suffering, injuries, and infections. Kanai and Piya witness the marginalized lives of people who suffer not only from poverty but from lack of medical infrastructure (Ghosh 115). Health in this context is tied to environment, poverty, and isolation—a key concern of Medical Humanities.

Arundhati Roy's *The Ministry of Utmost Happiness* (2017) portrays marginalized bodies, including the intersex protagonist Anjum, who navigates a world that medicalizes and stigmatizes non-normative identities (Roy 112). Roy highlights how medical institutions reinforce social exclusion. Roy also critiques the medical gaze that pathologizes non-normative bodies while highlighting the resilience of those living outside mainstream society (Roy 112).

The novel becomes a narrative of healing through community and empathy rather than clinical intervention.

Anita Nair's *Eating Wasps* (2018) deals with depression, trauma, and psychological abuse, focusing on female experiences often silenced in patriarchal settings. Nair presents mental health not merely as a medical condition but as a social crisis shaped by gendered violence (Nair 86). It is a multi-layered exploration of trauma, depression, and psychological healing, especially among women. The protagonist Sreelakshmi, a writer who dies by suicide, narrates stories of various women grappling with emotional wounds. Nair portrays mental health as deeply gendered, shaped by patriarchy, abuse, and societal neglect (Nair 90). The novel advocates for understanding mental illness within its socio-cultural context. It opens with the story of Sreelakshmi, a writer who committed suicide years ago. Her spirit narrates the inner worlds of women burdened by various forms of trauma, including sexual abuse, betrayal, loneliness, and body shaming (Nair 4). Mental health becomes central to the novel, as Sreelakshmi reflects, "People who choose death over life don't think they are dying. They think they are escaping" (Nair 7). It challenges the stigma around suicide and mental illness, emphasizing the emotional pain often overlooked in clinical settings. The novel presents multiple female characters — Najma, Urvashi, Megha, and others — who experience trauma linked to their bodies. The body becomes both a site of suffering and resistance, reflecting how gender intersects with Medical Humanities (Chatterjee 121). Urvashi's story of being burnt by acid, Najma's struggles with body image, and Megha's abusive relationship foreground how illness and trauma are gendered experiences (Nair 145). The narrative rejects clinical cures for emotional wounds, focusing instead on storytelling, memory, and solidarity among women as healing mechanisms. Sreelakshmi becomes a symbol of narrative healing, as her story offers solace to other women

(Mukherjee 139). Medical Humanities supports this idea that healing often requires empathy, listening, and understanding the patient's story — all of which *Eating Wasps* powerfully explores (Charon 49). Nair challenges the silence surrounding mental health issues in Indian society. Stigma of suicide, abuse, and depression prevents characters from seeking help, exposing the social roots of illness beyond physical symptoms (Nair 163). It resonates with Medical Humanities' approach of addressing cultural and emotional dimensions of illness.

Manjula Padmanabhan's *Harvest* (1997) is a dystopian exploration of organ trade, raising ethical questions about body commodification in a globalized world. The novel reflects the medical exploitation of the poor by the rich, questioning the morality of technological advances divorced from human empathy (Padmanabhan 42). Truly speaking, it is a dystopian representation of organ trade, depicting how bodies of the poor in India are commodified for the benefit of wealthy foreigners. Padmanabhan critiques medical exploitation in a globalized world, exposing how poverty transforms bodies into products (Padmanabhan 45). The play dramatizes the ethical dilemmas of bio-capitalism, questioning technological advancement devoid of empathy. It blends science fiction with medical history, centering on malaria research in colonial India. The text critiques the imperial appropriation of indigenous knowledge systems while celebrating alternative modes of healing (Ghosh 78). The novel challenges the Western-centric narrative of medical progress, highlighting local wisdom.

Further, we see that Amitav Ghosh's *The Calcutta Chromosome* (1995) integrates malaria research with myth and science, blurring boundaries between medical history and indigenous knowledge systems. Ghosh critiques Western medical imperialism while celebrating alternative healing traditions (Ghosh 78). These novels expose the intersections of medicine with caste, class, gender, and postcolonial realities. Healthcare in India is depicted not merely as a

service but as a site of power, exclusion, and resistance (Mukherjee 134). Medical Humanities in Indian English fiction thus becomes a narrative strategy to humanize medicine and highlight patient agency.

English novels often critique the ethical lapses in medical practices—be it the illegal organ trade, exploitation of the poor, or the medicalization of non-conforming bodies (Chatterjee 120). Female bodies and non-normative identities bear the brunt of both social oppression and medical neglect. Literature humanizes these struggles, providing voices to those erased from clinical narratives (Kapur 160). Mental health narratives in Indian English fiction expose the silence and stigma surrounding psychological disorders, especially among women, LGBTQ+ individuals, and poor (Nair 92). Narrative medicine, a key aspect of medical humanities, highlights the need for healthcare professionals to engage empathetically with patient stories. The novels discussed bridge this gap, allowing readers to confront emotional and ethical dimensions of illness (Charon 45).

Contemporary Indian English novels decode medical humanities by portraying illness not merely a biological condition but also a complex socio-cultural experience. The texts interrogate medical power, expose healthcare inequities, and highlight resilience and healing beyond clinical spaces. In doing so, literature becomes a vital site for reflecting on the ethics of care, patient agency, and the human condition in India. Medical Humanities offers a holistic approach to medicine, emphasizing empathy, ethics, and patient-centered care. It encourages healthcare professionals to see beyond symptoms and understand the human story behind every illness. As medicine continues to advance technologically, the need for Medical Humanities remains essential to preserve compassion and humanity in healthcare. Indian English novels serve powerful tools to decode medical humanities, presenting illness narratives that transcend clinical

settings. Through storytelling, these writers challenge medical authority, expose social injustices, and foreground emotional landscapes of health and suffering in India.

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